

ARRANGEMENT OF INFORMATION SIGNS ON THE STREETS OF THE HISTORICAL CITY. (IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE CITY OF SAMARKAND)

Matniyazov Zafarbek

Tashkent University of Architecture and Civil
Engineering, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ORCID: 0000-0001-7269-8127

e-mail: zafar18@mail.ru

Elmurodov Samidullo

Tashkent University of Architecture and Civil
Engineering, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ORCID: 0009-0005-2351-8122

samidullo1990@mail.ru

Tajibaev Jurat

Tashkent University of Architecture and Civil Engineering,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ORCID: 0009-0001-4544-8103

jurat0388@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10460973>

Annotation: In the article, an opinion is given about the projects studied and expected to be implemented on the subject of design code. At present, much attention is being paid to tourism, and the original appearance of buildings in urban areas is being lost, and advertising and information are taking over, and meaningless information is taking the place of historicity.

Anotatsiya: Maqolada dizayn kod mavzusi buyicha o'rganilgan va tadbiq etilishi kutilayotgan loyihalar xaqida fikr muloxaza qilinadi. Xozirda turizmga katta etibor qaratilayotganligi xamda shahar xududlarida binolarning asl ko'rinishi yo'qolib reklama va ma'lumotlar egallab olinayotganligi u yerda tarixiylik o'rnini manosiz malumotlar egallab bormoqda.

Key words: design code rules, historical cities, advertising objects, streets, urban planning, environmental design, landscape, small architectural forms, parametric.

Kalit so'zlar: dizayn-kod qoidalari, tarixiy shaharlar, reklama ob'yektlari, ko'chalar, shaharsozlik, atrof-muhit dizayni, landshaft, kichik me'moriy shakllar, parametrik.

INTRODUCTION. The concept of the design code appeared recently in our country compared to other countries. But today, along with the master plan and volumetric and spatial regulations, it is one of the three main means of creating a favorable urban environment, defined by the standard for the comprehensive development of areas. It combines the rules for the placement and exterior design of signboards, entrance groups of commercial buildings, non-stationary commercial objects and advertising structures, city overview and navigation elements. In this regard, experts from other countries have provided some information as a result of many researches and studies. Russian experts told how the design code of cities came about and why it is needed [1].

In fact, it is a set of rules for city streets. This rule is expected to be successful in many aspects, first of all, it is necessary to advertise the city with an aesthetic taste, and the most important thing is to make the general appearance of the city orderly and understandable for

tourists. Decisions have been made regarding the placement of advertisements and information. This must be followed.

A design code is a regulation that governs the design and placement of labels and advertisements. The introduction of the design code reduces "visual noise" - the irregular and excessive use of graphic materials and objects[2].

Entrepreneurs who believe that size and brightness are better for selling goods and services forget that they become indistinguishable in an endless stream of signs. Therefore, we need general rules that control and create a balance between commerce and the city itself, its houses, views and general atmosphere. was assigned to ensure the development and implementation of the regional "design code" taking into account the intended purpose of traditional architecture. Urban culture is also made taking into account the natural and climatic conditions of the area. The introduction of a design code by the city is a natural process, as a result of which entrepreneurs begin to compete not by the size and brightness of their sign, but by the quality of the product.

ANALYSIS OF THE RELEVANT LITERATURE. The design code is an important element of the architectural integrity of the city. "It's not just a set of rules and recommendations, it's a structure of how to shape the image of the city - signs, facades, non-capital construction projects, etc. Cities have rules, but rarely do they have a design code that everyone follows- from developers to entrepreneurs.

Therefore, street advertising banners, entrance groups, landscaping elements allow to create a visually coherent image of the urban space for perception, taking into account the good design code, the historical identity of the place and its characteristics.

The design code directly affects the psycho-emotional state of the city's inhabitants. It is noted that today architects must create aesthetics, create a set of strict regulatory rules that define the Design code based on the standards of buildings and, on the one hand, are responsible for the safety of the building, and on the other hand, determine the conditions it is permissible. With the design code in the living environment, revealing the individuality of people and telling the history of the country, instilling respect for each other, educating - this belongs to the category of the intangible world and affects human culture[3]. From culture we can immediately build a bridge to the development of the best human qualities. When we are in a closed environment, we are unlikely to spit on the ground or litter in a landscaped, landscaped area. Therefore, the design code helps to create a cultural framework that does not limit human freedom, but teaches respect for one's neighbor.

The design code describes the placement and appearance of information and

Figure 1. Information board

advertising structures that can be embodied as billboards, boards, plaques, window dressings and awnings. You can see festive decorations around the city, recommendations on how to properly place city navigation, address display stands. Based on the architectural and urban importance of the area, the general requirements for the placement and design of parking pavilions, non-stationary trade facilities: kiosks, pavilions of the fir markets have been assembled[4]. Design - code aims at a systematic approach to the urban environment, forming an orderly, clear and aesthetically attractive image of the city. Information and advertising structures Types of constructions The project code regulates the placement and appearance of 3 types of information and advertising structures: independent and address plates installed on the facade of buildings. Information and advertising structures on the facade Main labels, panel brackets, roof mounts, information boards, transparent structures, etc. Information and advertising structures Information stand, Road sign, navigation stele, navigation sign festival decoration.

General requirements Classification The section contains rules for 5 types of independent structures: information stands, masts, navigation stelae, navigation signs and structures intended for festival decoration. Structures that do not fall into any of these categories cannot be placed[5].

These rules apply to all independent information and advertising structures, regardless of their type and location. Installation and use of information and advertising structures should not interfere with the operation of engineering infrastructure objects. Structures must be safe, designed, manufactured, assembled and installed in accordance with construction norms and regulations, as well as regulatory legal documents containing requirements for the relevant type of structures. The owner of an information or advertising facility that does not meet the design requirements of the code is obliged to dismantle it.

When performing work on installation and dismantling of information structures, it is necessary to take all measures to ensure the personal safety of people and the safety of movement, as well as the safety of buildings, structures, properties. Any information and advertising structures should be installed taking into account wind and snow loads. - The use of linear video screens and panels that serve as the front of the information and design of the PVC fabric banner is prohibited.

- The use of flashing and flashing elements is prohibited.
- In Russia, it is recommended to use it only in informational and advertising structures, if necessary, increase the information in English. In this case, the font of the text in English should be reduced by 2

Figure 2. Information board.

times the font version in Russian. It is not recommended to use other languages, especially languages with different writing systems. (Fig. 2.)

Separate structures should not obstruct the passage of special equipment The distance from free structures to light poles should be at least 2 m.

Billboards, including video screens, are prohibited. It is forbidden to place information and advertising on fences 2m. Placing information and advertising on traffic lights, road signs and other technical structures is prohibited (Fig. 3).

An information stand is a small independent structure for placing advertisements, references, area maps and announcements. The information stand can be equipped with external lighting, if the cable is hidden in the structure of the stand. The maximum total height of the stand is 2.1 m, the maximum width is 1.5 m. (Fig. 4).

The information stand can be made with one-sided and two-sided information fields. The back side of the one-sided design should be filled with a decorative frame. If the stands are not used for advertising, then it is permissible to place them in groups, no more than 3 designs in each group. Information stands are installed on all types of streets and are designed primarily for pedestrians. Stands functionally connected to buildings can be placed close to the facade.

Figure 3. Billboard.

Figure 4. Information stand

should be filled with a decorative frame. If the stands are not used for advertising, then it is permissible to place them in groups, no more than 3 designs in each group. Information stands are installed on all types of streets and are designed primarily for pedestrians. Stands functionally connected to buildings can be placed close to the facade. The information booth should not block the entrance to buildings or shops from the side of the road. The distance between the stands must be at least 100 m, while it is allowed to place up to 3 stands in a row (DIVIDING THEM INTO GROUPS), if not used for advertising. The distance between stands or groups of stands should be at least 100 m from other information and advertising structures. The minimum distance between stands and other structures not less than 60 m is 120 m (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Information stand.

A road sign is a small independent mobile structure on which advertisements and menus are placed. Also, the pavement sign can be used in cases where the point of sale does not have its own sign. The period of placement of the advertising column is limited by the opening hours of the point of sale. The maximum height of the column is 1.2 m and the maximum width is 0.8 m. Columns should be combined

with the surrounding buildings and small architectural forms, should not create visual noise, so the colors should not be bright. The appearance of the column depends on the area where it is installed.

A navigation stele is an independent information structure designed to place information about the surrounding area, points of interest and elements of transport infrastructure. The information is primarily aimed at pedestrians. Navigation stelae are designed to be placed on the main and secondary streets of the settlement with a dense flow of pedestrians (including tourists), as well as on the borders of the village in places after natural objects, which are the most popular among tourists. The stele should stand in a good visible place. The pedestrian information system should be continuous. It is recommended to install navigation stele at a step of no more than 300 m. The location of the structure should be convenient for pedestrians and people with reduced mobility and should not interfere with mechanized street cleaning. The navigation stela should be located at least 4 m from the road sign or traffic light in the direction of movement. It is recommended to place Stellar near public transport stops and near entrances to major social organizations (Figure 6).

KORXONA	brendning nomi, tijorat belgisi
KAFE	tovarlar va xizmatlar turi
	logotip
	qo'shimcha ma'lumot
24/7	ish tartibi
	ruxsat etilgan zona turar joy

Figure 6. Information board.

Making advertising information boards placed in and around buildings based on the rules of placement.

1. Visual suggestion.
2. The main character.
3. The list of general trade centers and companies.
4. Table of data.
5. Data dock.
6. The messages in the display windows are images.
7. Panel design.
8. Board at the border of the commercial object.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it should be said that the design code was developed for nothing and its implementation is not intended to give more taste and aesthetic pleasure to our country. It is self-evident that this arrangement should be approached from the side of style and design, and the contribution of designers will be great. Together with them, a solution to this problem will be found. Design proposals are given to each street, while preserving the generality of the building. Design codes are developed and applied to each building based on the requirements. It is developed separately without leaving out small elements. The layout of information banners and directions, which are easy to read for both pedestrians and car drivers, is taken into account.

There are opportunities to use small architectural forms regulated by design code rules. By correctly and effectively using small architectural forms, opportunities to attract more tourists and create amenities will open up in our historical cities. As a rule, it should be noted

that when placing small architectural forms in public areas, it is necessary to comply with the rules of the Design Code, which is now being implemented in Uzbekistan, and to take into account that they do not block its elements or disturb the movement of people. To leave a warm impression of our country to every visiting guest, to young and old representatives of our country, to improve service in our city.

References:

1. Дизайн-код правила размещения и оформления нестационарных торговых объектов в псков дизайн-код псков 2018
2. В Узбекистане внедрят «дизайн-код» городской среды - <https://kun.uz/ru/news/2020/11/29/v-uzbekistanevnedryat-dizayn-kod-gorodskoy-sredy>
3. Строительство и эксплуатация объектов ландшафтной архитектуры. Теодоронский В.С. и др. 2008. Глава 7.
4. Saidov A.A. "Ergonomika". Darslik. Toshkent. 2018.
5. ZX Adilov, ZE Matniyazov, DM Tadjibaeva, JX Tadjibaev, SS Elmurodov. "Some Aspects of the Organization of "Corridors of Health" in the Historical Centers of the Cities of Uzbekistan" \ \ European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630) 16, 105-112, 2022
6. DG kizi Asatova, ZE Matniyazov. "The Spatial Formation and Architecture of the Fire Temple of Zoroastrianism" \ \ Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity 6, 488-500, 2022.
7. ZX Adilov, ZE Matniyazov, DM Tadjibaeva, JX Tadjibaev, SS Elmurodov. "Landscape design projects for 4r-173 call-mountain road side" \ \ International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and ..., 2020.
8. S Elmurodov, Z Matniyazov, U Saidxonova, D Abdujabborova "Principles of Location of NonStationary Trade Objects in the Zoning Method" \ \ Journal of Architectural Design 13, 8-13.
9. D Shoumarova, J Tajibaev, S Elmurodov, U Saidkhanova, Z Matniyazov "Regulation Of Advertising Objects in the Development of the Design Code of Historical Cities. (In The Case of the City of Bukhara)" \ \ Journal of Architectural Design 13, 56-63
10. US Z Adilov, Z Matniyozov, J Tojiboev, U Daminova. "Improvement of the environmental situation of the aral region through landscape design" \ \ International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research 9 (4), 3450-3455, 2020.
11. J Tajibaev. "Определение исторических центров городов и разработка правил дизайн-кода для них (на примере Самарканда и Бухары)" \ \ Journal of Architectural Design 13, 50-55, 2022.